

Differential equation and mass spectrum for elementary particles

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Abstract

I hypothesize that there is an infinite mass spectrum for leptons, for up-type and for down-type quarks.

I try a least squares method to obtain the possible mass spectrum $M(i)$: the aim is to make a prediction for the masses not yet observed, like for the Mendeleev periodic table.

I write a possible differential equation for the mass spectrum of the elementary particles.

1 Introduction

I think that it is possible to estimate the mass spectrum of an infinite generation in the standard model.

I try a simple law, inspired by the Balmer series for $\gamma = -2$:

$$M(n) = \alpha + \beta n^\gamma \quad (1)$$

where γ is a half-integer, or integer, value.

I will get a quantum equation for the mass spectrum:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \partial_{xx} l(x) + (\alpha_l + \eta_l x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)}) l(x) = (\alpha_l + \beta_l n^\gamma) l(x) \quad (2)$$

The three series (quarks and leptons) have an error in the approximation if γ is half-integer; if γ is real, then the mass spectrum is without errors, because of there are three data with three parameters.

I minimize the error using the gradient descent on the error function:

$$E = \sum_n \left[\frac{M(n) - \alpha - \beta n^\gamma}{M(n)} \right]^2 \quad (3)$$

I obtain the three series for half-integer exponents:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{uct\dots}(n) &= 1.98300530837242992 + 0.31807526172086348 n^{12} = \alpha_u + \beta_u n^{\gamma_u} \\
M_{dsb\dots}(n) &= 4.67920930705276248 + 0.123512751460342719 n^{9.5} = \alpha_d + \beta_d n^{\gamma_d} \\
M_{e\mu\tau\dots}(n) &= -0.309032402380580531 + 0.819900950498734082 n^7 = \alpha_l + \beta_l n^{\gamma_l}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

with errors $E_{uct\dots} = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$, $E_{dsb\dots} = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $E_{e\mu\tau\dots} = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$

The masses in this serie are:

$\gamma = n/2$		
$M_{uct\dots}$	$M_{dsb\dots}$	$M_{e\mu\tau\dots}$
2.301081 MeV	4.802722 MeV	0.510868 MeV
1.304819 GeV	94.111994 MeV	104.638290 MeV
169.040218 GeV	4.215471 GeV	1.792814 GeV
5.336419 TeV	64.760933 GeV	13.432948 GeV
77.655095 TeV	539.424422 GeV	64.054453 GeV
692.380613 TeV	3.048943 TeV	229.519483 GeV

If there is no constraint on the exponent, the three series are;

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{uct\dots}(n) &= 2.01347391599403587 + 0.286526084005964126 n^{12.1172630474481873} \\
M_{dsb\dots}(n) &= 4.67125779629747082 + 0.128742203702529001 n^{9.45455624064027989} \\
M_{e\mu\tau}(n) &= -0.34439344630781693 + 0.855392356307816903 n^{6.95329980131879852}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

with errors: $E_{uct\dots} = 5.9 \cdot 10^{-38}$, $E_{dsb\dots} = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-38}$ and $E_{e\mu\tau\dots} = 2.0 \cdot 10^{-38}$; the exponents in the formulas are near half-integer values, so that could exist a theory with mass spectrum that has semi integer numbers like eigenvalues. The non-yellows values are possible new leptons and quark masses.

$\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$		
$M_{uct\dots}$	$M_{dsb\dots}$	$M_{e\mu\tau\dots}$
2.3 MeV	4.8 MeV	0.510999 MeV
1.275 GeV	95 MeV	105.658367 MeV
173.21 GeV	4.18 GeV	1.776840 GeV
5.655664 TeV	63.381570 GeV	13.135832 GeV
84.482660 TeV	522.607980 GeV	61.988474 GeV
769.533547 TeV	2.929519 TeV	220.233622 GeV

I think that three signals could be measured: the $\approx 26\text{Gev}$ signal for the dilepton $M_7(4)\overline{M}_7(4) \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ that

Mass spectrum for leptons and quarks with formula with half-integer exponents

decay in two aligned photons, or the $\approx 126\text{GeV}$ signal for the meson $M_{9.5}(4)\overline{M}_{9.5}(4) \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ or the $\approx 124\text{GeV}$ $M_7(5)\overline{M}_7(5) \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ gammas emission (or $\approx 0.5\%$ gamma misalignment through the 125GeV Higgs intermediate production for the meson); the mass of the pair matter-antimatter of $M_7(5)$ and $M_{9.5}(4)$ are near to the Higgs mass, so that the measure could be problematic.

2 Differential equation for the particle masses

If the mass spectrum approximation is correct, then it is possible to write a differential equation with eigenvalues equal to the masses of the particles.

A simple solution is (\hbar is an arbitrary little parameter):

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \partial_{xx}\Psi(x) + V(x)\Psi(x) = \lambda\Psi(x) = n^\gamma\Psi(x) = M_\gamma\Psi(x) \quad (6)$$

so that the solution is a potential that satisfies the equation, where γ is the exponent of the elementary particle serie; the Wentzel-Kramers-Brillouin approximation is:

$$\Psi(x) = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}S(x)} = \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\sum_{n=0}^{\infty}\left(\frac{\hbar}{i}\right)^n S_n(x)\right] \simeq \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}S_0 + S_1\right] \quad (7)$$

$$S'_0 = \pm\sqrt{2(\lambda - V(x))} \quad (8)$$

$$0 = 2S'_0S'_1 + S''_0 \quad (9)$$

$$S'_1 = -\frac{d}{dx}\ln(S'_0) = -\frac{d}{dx}\ln(\sqrt{2(\lambda - V(x))}) \quad (10)$$

$$S_1 = \ln(A) - \ln(\sqrt{\lambda - V(x)}) \quad (11)$$

so that the solution of the differential equation is:

$$\Psi_{\pm}(x) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{2(\lambda - V(x))}} \exp\left(\pm\frac{i}{\hbar}\int_{x_0}^x dx\sqrt{2(\lambda - V(x))}\right) \quad (12)$$

the WKB solution with n^γ is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2}\partial_{xx}\Psi(x) + V(x)\Psi(x) = n^\gamma\Psi(x) \quad (13)$$

$$V(x) = \eta x^k \quad (14)$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2}\partial_{xx}\Psi(x) + \eta x^k\Psi(x) = n^\gamma\Psi(x) \quad (15)$$

$$S_0 = \int_{x_0}^x dx \sqrt{2(\lambda - \eta x^k)} = \int_{u_0}^u du \lambda^{\frac{1}{k}} \sqrt{2(\lambda - \eta \lambda u^k)} = \lambda^{\frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{2}} A(x) \quad (16)$$

$$E_n \propto n^{\frac{2k}{k+2}} = n^\gamma \quad (17)$$

$$V_\gamma(x) = x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)} \quad (18)$$

there are three γ values for the leptons, quarks-up and quarks-down:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_l = n^7 &\implies V_l(x) = \eta x^{-14/5} \\ \lambda_u = n^{12} &\implies V_u(x) = \eta x^{-12/5} \\ \lambda_d = n^{9.5} &\implies V_d(x) = \eta x^{-38/15} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

so that the differential equation for the mass spectrum could be:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2}\partial_{xx}l(x) + (\alpha_l + \eta_l x^{-14/5})l(x) = (\alpha_l + \beta_l n^7)l(x) \quad (20)$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2}\partial_{xx}u(x) + (\alpha_u + \eta_u x^{-12/5})u(x) = (\alpha_u + \beta_u n^{12})u(x) \quad (21)$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2}\partial_{xx}d(x) + (\alpha_d + \eta_d x^{-38/15})d(x) = (\alpha_d + \beta_d n^{9.5})d(x) \quad (22)$$

where the eigenvalues of differential equation for the elementary particles coincides with the experimental data.

It is possible to obtain a mass potential, in some toy models in classical physics; a rolling ball of mass m can move in a bowl surface, with the component of the gravity force $m \cdot g$ along the surface equal to the field force \mathcal{E}_γ (each solution of this differential equation is a motion with the mass potential V_γ)

$$g \frac{y'(x)}{\sqrt{1 + y'(x)^2}} = -\partial_x V_\gamma(x) = \frac{2\gamma}{2-\gamma} \eta_\gamma x^{-1+2\gamma/(2-\gamma)} = \eta_\gamma \mu x^{-1+\mu} = \mathcal{E}_\gamma \quad (23)$$

$$-g \leq \eta_\gamma \mu x^{-1+\mu} \leq g \quad (24)$$

the oscillation in the case of $\gamma = 1$ is an ideal harmonic oscillator in the interval; there exist potential with rational exponent in the real world, because of the holonomic constraint that change the fields with constraint reactions

(the interval define a brane, if there is a surface of revolution that generate a bowl for the ball oscillations): the mass potential V_γ could be a surface, or string, constraint of a higher dimension field force.

If there is a solution in a possible Quantum Gravity for wavefunctions on a surface with quantized level, then the mass spectrum of these wavefunctions could be the elementary particles.

It is possible to use an arbitrary arithmetic function $f(n) = \sum_s a_s n^s$ to obtain the spectrum of the elementary particles with the WKB approximation: the potential for an arbitrary arithmetic function is a Puiseux serie with an asymptotic approximation for great n that is the differential equation in this article; so that the potential in the article is the asymptotic solution for a simple arithmetic function that give the spectrum for the observable elementary particle; so that the theory is the path for each possible mass spectrum.

If there is a quantum generation of the particles, then it is possible that the Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata matrix can exist for each particle generation: if there is an energy of an hadron different from the energy level, then the quark (it can happen for leptons), could exist in a superposition of quantum states.

I am thinking that the elementary particles with eigenvalues n^7 , $n^{9.5}$ and n^{12} could be the class of the observable elementary particles in the range of observable energy; if it is so, then it could be possible that it exist the class of particle with mass $M_\gamma(n)$ with γ half-integer and integer, with an infinity of interaction field and an infinity of elementary particles, and the human observer can detect only some energy spectra and only some energy interaction fields (only in the black hole proximity the complete class of elementary particles could be observable).

I am thinking that constraints in the inelastic collision is equivalent to Cabibbo–Kobayashi–Maskawa matrix constraints: the superposition of the quantum particle can absorb the excess of the total energy that cannot be absorbed by the particle creation, so that hadrons can exist in an overlap of quark-types, like in Kaon anomaly; I hypothesize that for each value of the energy of the mass serie there are quantum states (quantum eigenfunctions); for example if the total energy of the particle is not an eigenvalue of the quantum equation $E_\gamma \neq M_\gamma(n) \forall n$, then:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \partial_{xx} \psi_\gamma(x) + [\alpha_\gamma + \eta_\gamma x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)}] \psi_\gamma(x) = E_\gamma \psi_\gamma(x) \quad (25)$$

so that exist non-normalizable quantum state could be a solution on a string:

$$\Psi_\gamma(x) = \sum_n [a_n x^n + a_{k|\mu} |x^{k|\mu}|] x^n e^{ik_\gamma x} + \sum_n b_n [a_n x^n + a_{k|\mu} |x^{k|\mu}|] e^{-ik_\gamma x} \quad (26)$$

with $\mu = 2\gamma/(2-\gamma)$ that satisfy the quantum equation with energy E_γ , with a serie that does not terminate; this could be true for photon absorpction by a single atom, or a phonon absorpction for a single quantum harmonic oscillator for the Schrödinger equation.

The potential and the coordinate could be string potential, or a brane with higher complexity theory, but it seem that a single dimension is sufficient for the theory.

The black holes could produce couple of particles of unobservable γ -type

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \partial_{xx} \psi_\gamma(x) + [\alpha_\gamma + \eta_\gamma x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)}] \psi_\gamma(x) = (\alpha_\gamma + \beta_\gamma n^\gamma) \psi_\gamma(x) \quad (27)$$

where the only observable effect should be the space deformation, because of each γ -type particle has an observable mass, so that every unobservable particle in the energy field (and interaction) should be observable due to gravitational effects: astronomical measure.

If everything is right, and measurable, then the force unification is an theory of infinite interaction fields.

If everything is right, then the elementary particle masses are string oscillation that generate the measurable masses.

3 Quantum gravity solution for the mass spectrum

There are infinite metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ for gravitational field, each metric tensor has a Lagrangian $L(g^{ik}, \partial_r g^{ik})$, so that exist a potential $V(g^{ik})$ that warp the space with the arbitrary g^{ik} metric tensor; the Schrödinger equation has not a deductive demonstration from other laws, so that if there is a physical law that give the experimental results (the mass spectrum) without a deductive demonstration, then the physical law is right, if each other physical results does not contradict the law.

If there is an automatic research of Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}(g^{ik}, \partial_r g^{lm})$, and potential, from metric tensors (with automatic software) that have an arbitrary gravitational potential that has a simple form (like the integer or half-interger, mass spectrum) then it could be possible to write an Hamiltonian density with diagonal metric tensor:

$$i\hbar\partial_t\Psi(g^{\mu\nu}, t) = \mathcal{H}(g^{\mu\nu}, \partial_{g^{\alpha\alpha}})\Psi(g^{\mu\nu}, t) \quad (28)$$

that give the mass spectrum; if there is a differential equation with a potential that has rational values, then the metric tensor satisfies the differential equation, because of there is a one-to-one correspondence between metric and potentials, if the kinetic energy operator is a scalar value:

$$\hat{T} = -\frac{c^3\hbar^2}{16\pi G}g^{00}g^{aa}g^{aa}\partial_{g^{aa}}\partial_{g^{aa}} \quad (29)$$

for a diagonal metric tensor, and the potential is obtained by automatic search, then it could be possible to obtain a quantum solution with mass spectrum from metric tensor

A Solution of the differential equation of the mass equations

The asymptotic solution of the masses equation can be obtained using the Wentzel-Kramers-Brillouin approximation, for each potential:

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \partial_{xx} \Psi_\gamma(x) + [\alpha_\gamma + \eta_\gamma x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)}] \Psi_\gamma(x) = E_\gamma \Psi_\gamma(x) \\
\Psi_\gamma(x \rightarrow \infty) & \simeq e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} S} = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} [S_0 + \frac{\hbar}{i} S_1 + (\frac{\hbar}{i})^2 S_2 + \dots]} \\
& -\hbar^2 \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_0'' + S_1'' + \left(\frac{i}{\hbar} S_0' + S_1' \right)^2 \right] + 2 [\alpha_\gamma + \eta_\gamma x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)}] \Psi_\gamma(x) \simeq 2E_\gamma \Psi_\gamma(x) \\
& -i\hbar S_0'' - \hbar^2 S_1'' + S_0' S_0' - 2i\hbar S_0' S_1' - \hbar^2 S_1' S_1' + 2 [\alpha_\gamma + \eta_\gamma x^{2\gamma/(2-\gamma)}] \Psi_\gamma(x) \simeq 2E_\gamma \Psi_\gamma(x) \\
& \begin{cases} S_0' S_0' = 2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma) \\ S_0'' + 2S_0' S_1' = 0 \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

the lepton and quark equation has $\mu = \frac{2\gamma}{2-\gamma} < 0$, and $V_\gamma = \alpha_\gamma + \eta_\gamma x^\mu$ so that

$$\begin{aligned}
S_0(x \rightarrow \infty) & = \int dx \sqrt{2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma)} \\
S_1'(x \rightarrow \infty) & = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{S_0''}{S_0'} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} \ln(S_0') = \frac{d}{dx} \ln[(S_0')^{-1/2}] \implies S_1 = \ln \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma)}} \right) \\
\Psi_\gamma(x \rightarrow \infty) & = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma)}} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int dx \sqrt{2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma)}} \simeq \begin{cases} \pm i \frac{x^{-\mu/2}}{\sqrt{2\eta_\gamma}} \exp \left(\pm \frac{\sqrt{2\eta_\gamma}}{\hbar(1+\mu/2)} x^{1+\mu/2} \right) & \text{if } \mu > 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(E_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma)}} \exp \left(\pm ix \sqrt{\frac{2(E_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma)}{\hbar^2}} \right) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

I choose the physical solution that goes to zero exponentially; the solutions for non-observable particle with $\mu > 0$:

$$\Psi_\gamma = \sum_n a_n x^{n-\mu/2} \exp \left(-\frac{\text{sign}(1+\mu/2)}{1+\mu/2} \frac{\sqrt{2\eta_\gamma}}{\hbar} x^{1+\mu/2} \right) = \sum_n a_n x^{n-\mu/2} \exp(-k_\gamma x^{1+\mu/2}) \tag{32}$$

it is possible to terminate the series for some value of the energy $E_\gamma = M_\gamma$, and the terms of the serie are $a_{n+k\mu/2}$.

If the energy E_γ is near to M_γ , then the terms of serie are near the serie that terminate, and there are infinite excited states, and there are only emission for the level $M_\alpha < E_\gamma$ (for the energy conservation).

The currently observable solutions, with $k_\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{2(E_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma)}{\hbar^2}}$, are:

$$\Psi_\gamma(x) = \sum_n a_n x^n e^{ik_\gamma x} + \sum_n b_n x^n e^{-ik_\gamma x} \tag{33}$$

a physical solution terminate, so that there are only a little number of excited state of the energy M_γ , the problem of this solution is that the wavefunction is singular $\Psi(x \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \infty$.

If $\mu < 0$ then $\mu = -|\mu|$, and the equation for the terms of the serie is:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_{xx} \Psi_\gamma(x) &= \frac{2\eta_\gamma}{\hbar^2} x^{-|\mu|} \Psi_\gamma(x) + \frac{2(\alpha_\gamma - E_\gamma)}{\hbar^2} \Psi_\gamma(x) \\ a_n n(n-1)x^{n-2} + a_n 2ik_\gamma n x^{n-1} - a_n x^n k_\gamma^2 &= \frac{2\eta_\gamma}{\hbar^2} a_n x^{n-|\mu|} + \frac{2(\alpha_\gamma - E_\gamma)}{\hbar^2} a_n x^n \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_n(n+2)(n+1) - a_{n+|\mu|} \frac{2\eta_\gamma}{\hbar^2} = -a_{n+1} 2ik_\gamma(n+1) + \left[a_n k_\gamma^2 + \frac{2(\alpha_\gamma - E_\gamma)}{\hbar^2} \right] a_n \\ b_n(n+2)(n+1) - b_{n+|\mu|} \frac{2\eta_\gamma}{\hbar^2} = b_{n+1} 2ik_\gamma(n+1) + \left[b_n k_\gamma^2 + \frac{2(\alpha_\gamma - E_\gamma)}{\hbar^2} \right] b_n \end{array} \right. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

only the values that terminate the serie give eigenvalues for the differential equation.

The solution to infinity is a oscillation in a free space with a perturbation:

$$\Psi_\gamma(x \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(E_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma - \eta_\gamma x^{-|\mu|})}} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int dx \sqrt{2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma)}} \simeq \frac{\left(1 + \frac{\eta_\gamma}{2(E_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma)} x^{-|\mu|}\right)}{\sqrt{2(E_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma)}} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int dx \sqrt{2(E_\gamma - V_\gamma)}} \quad (35)$$

but this solution has a singularity $\Psi(x \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \infty$.

There is a solution without singularity, with the right mass spectrum: the masses can be oscillations in a finite range of x , with regressive and progressive waves, in a string of unknown dimension $2\pi n \sqrt{\frac{\hbar^2}{2(M_\gamma - \alpha_\gamma)}}$; the string can be open, or close; the problem is that there is an arbitrary constant \hbar , and an arbitrary dimension of the string (each width can give the mass spectrum).

References

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